

THE ROLE OF MANIPULATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article describes the importance and role of manipulation in English language teaching and pedagogy. In addition, the types of manipulation and the opinions of various scientists about it are highlighted. This article is a very useful resource for researchers and English teachers.

Key words: manipulation, manipulator, oral communication, motivation, modern linguistics.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili o'qitishda va pedagogikada manipulyatsiyaning ahamiyati va roli haqida bayon qilingan. Bundan tashqari manipulyatsiyaning turlari va u haqda turli xil olimlarning fikrlari yoritib berilgan. Ushbu maqola tadqiqotchilar ingliz tili o'qituvchilari uchun juda foydali manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: manipulyatsiya, manipulyator, og'zaki muloqot, motivatsiya, zamonaviy lingvistika.

Аннотация: в этой статье описывается важность и роль манипуляции в обучении английскому языку и педагогике. Кроме того, выделены виды манипуляции и мнения о ней различных ученых. Эта статья является очень полезным ресурсом для исследователей и преподавателей английского языка.

Ключевые слова: манипуляция, манипулятор, устное общение, мотивация, современная лингвистика.

It is the fact that modern linguistics studies language as a form of social practice, focuses on the entire range of humanitarian knowledge, which makes it possible to explain and describe the various processes of verbal communication. Linguistic is focused on solving some problems, which implies a diverse use of linguistic data not

only to study objects from other areas of science, but also to fulfill human needs for productive, effective communication. For teaching language, effectively all English teachers need manipulation. Manipulation is main teaching tool in pedagogy and it is complex topic. Because none of us wants to become a victim of manipulation. But any teacher, not only an English teacher but also other subject teachers such as math, physics or information technology teachers sooner or later, applies it in work with children. There is a question: What is “manipulation”?

There are several meanings of manipulation they are:

- manage
- use
- control
- operate

Several authors and researches discussed the term “manipulation”:

1. Bessenov B.N.

“A form of spiritual influence of hidden domination, carried out by force”.

2. Volkogonov D.A.

“Dominance over the spiritual state, management of changes in the inner world”

3. Goodin R.

“Covert use of power (force) contrary to the alleged will of another”

4. Yokoyama O.T

“Fraudulent indirect influence in the interest of the manipulator”¹

This important trend is sometimes called the build-and-destroy trend. Students instinctively explore, deconstruct, and reconstruct objects. Young students have a very strong desire to touch everything they see. Manipulation includes skillful or proficient management or control of behavior by intelligence. Great for motor learning. Children and students are naturally inclined to explore and discover which contributes greatly to

¹ Брыжак Анастасия Леонидовна «Использование педагогического манипуляторного дискурса на примере английского языка»

education. This trend causes obvious joy in directed games, board work, and constructive projects. Schools should provide students with activities that provide opportunities for expression through manipulation. Motivation and enthusiasm are greatly enhanced when constructive and artistic activities are introduced into schools through a strong interest in the concrete and objective, and a strong interest. Object theory and manual theory deftly extend this realm of assignment ordering. Teachers need to make extensive use of manipulation in classroom operations.

“Manipulator”-a person who obtains his goal by deceiving and deliberately exercising control over other people. Evaluation, conferment hand on activities are main tool of manipulating the children. For example if the teacher say the student, “I give you to point” pupil learn well in order not to get two mark.

On the one hand, there are two notions about manipulation:

Firstly Manipulation is an attempt to manipulate people's minds, make them propaganda (attempts to spread certain ideas and theories, propaganda) and exert psychological influence. The word "manipulation" comes from the Latin word² "manus" - hand (manipulus - palm, handful). The word is used in the dictionary to refer to tricks and tricks performed with manual dexterity.

Secondly, "Linguistic manipulation" is one of the most important problems of modern linguistics. The theory of speech effect deals with several concepts, such as "speech effect", "speech manipulation", "linguistic manipulation", which are used both as related concepts and as opposite concepts. Except that, one can be defined as a component of the other. The influence of speech has an intentional character, when an individual is influenced, and the influence is carried out verbally. Linguistic manipulation is an effective communication between the speaker and the receiver, in which the speaker tries to achieve the desired result by observing the receiver's behavior with the help of speech. P.B. Parshin describes this phenomenon in a broad sense as influencing the consciousness of an individual or a group of individuals with

² Сергей Кара Мурза, «Манипуляция сознанием. XXI век», «Алгоритм» 2015, 11 с.
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the help of linguistic means, and in a narrow sense as the formation of speech capable of changing attitudes, and calls it the receiver's method of action.³

More recently, language has been viewed not only as a means of verbal communication, but also as an interaction based on specific tactics and strategies. Most research has focused on informational discourse, which constitutes the learning process. On the other hand, another type of manipulative discourse that encourages students to actively acquire knowledge is prevalent in educational discourse. This type of discourse also draws attention to specific moments in the story and draws attention to the topic.

As a future teacher, I need to master them in order to be able to stop my students' attempts to manipulate them, so I wanted to cover child tricks as a separate sub-paragraph.

E. Shostrom defines children as excellent manipulators. He distinguishes several types:⁴

1) the most common of these is the "little rag". This passive dependent child manipulates his parents using his extreme helplessness and indecision, his chronic forgetfulness and inattention. Early on, discovering the strength of his seeming weakness, he chooses the role of helpless and stupid. He is not just lazy, as many people think. He is cunning as a fox. He is smart enough to successfully manipulate adults and make them do everything for him.

2) The second type of child manipulator can be called a "little dictator". He controls adults with pouting, stubbornness, disobedience, stamping his feet.

3) The third type of children's manipulator is Freddy the Fox. He began life as a crybaby, and as he soon discovered, tears are paid for with attention. He himself had not yet had time to figure out why he burst into tears, but he was already being consoled, affectionately stroked and, it seems, more loved. Before school, he honed his

³ Паршин П.Б. Речевое воздействие: основные формы и разновидности / П.Б. Паршин // Рекламный текст: Семиотика и лингвистика. – М.: Эксмо, 2000. – 372 с.

⁴ Брыжак Анастасия Леонидовна «Использование педагогического манипуляторного дискурса на примере английского языка»

tear mechanism, and at school, he got the opportunity to use his secret weapon for its intended purpose.

4) The fourth type of little manipulator is "cruel Tom". His characteristic feature is a violent temperament. He pushes, bullies, calls children names, fights and spits. Early, he realized that an explosive mixture of hatred and fear makes people well governed. Therefore, he became an aspiring bully. More than anything, he hates authority. His unshakable confidence quickly turns into arrogance and absolute faith in his own strength

5) The fifth type of children's manipulator is "George - a competitor", or striving to be the first. This is a kind of combination of Tom and Freddie. Usually George grows up in families where there are two boys, and the youngest masters the science of competition from an early age, winning his equal place in this world. School is the best training ground for his exercises in this area.

Speech methods of manipulative influence in English lessons.

When someone is trying to influence someone else, there are different types of ways they can do this. Manipulative influence is when the person trying to influence someone else aims to achieve his or her own selfish goals, which can harm the person receiving the influence. Non-manipulative hidden influence, on the other hand, is when the person trying to influence someone else has the goal of helping the recipient without him or her realizing it. When adults talk about "manipulation," they usually mean using hidden tactics to get what they want. In business, for example, this might involve using language to control or influence someone else. However, this is different from simply using force or manipulation to get what you want. For example, if you try to convince someone by using forceful language, you are actually manipulating him or her. However, if you use language to get what you want without using force, you are being manipulative. They found to the controllability of information presentation. This is manifested in the fragmentation of information presentation and the formation of specific appraisals that determine its perceptual properties. Such manipulation of information allows the influencing party to evoke the necessary emotional response in the recipient and to impose a particular conception of reality.

Manipulation in educational communication is an integral part of school communication. Teachers encounter children with very different abilities and personalities. However, since everyone has to work together, a subtle psychological game begins that requires the use of various means of manipulation.

Who does not perform this task - I give him 2 points! The rating system itself assumes such an operation. With points, scores, grades, images, stickers, and a grading system, teachers can choose options within the system, but not outside.

Manipulation is a two-way process. As observation shows, students are skilled manipulators. They also turn to teachers. In addition, students evaluate both lessons and teachers, but only show their grades to teachers in the form of attitudes toward learning, school, and especially teachers. Educational discourse emphasizes manipulation strategies aimed at controlling situations by controlling people's behavior. Manipulation occurs when one side of the communication has a strategy and the other side does not and is forced to follow. Manipulation also occurs when one strategy absorbs her second strategy for a strategic duel. H. The first one is more powerful and is pushed to the other side.

Manipulation pedagogy emerges as an effective means of organizing human relationships in the educational process. Manipulative pedagogy never means that a child is manipulated against his or her interests, which of course happens, but this shows the acquisition of the destructive character of manipulation by pedagogy. Constructive manipulation in is a positive tool for child development, development is much more productive and focused, and allows for a deeper self-actualization than authoritative pedagogy provides. However, manipulation education, like authoritative education, is based on the premise that the mentor knows more about the pet's needs than the student does, himself does, and that the educator can follow the educational goals he has determined. Organize a movement (development) towards within the framework of operational pedagogy, educators should not explicitly present educational goals to students in order to avoid or demonstrate direct formative, directive, non-violent influences on students. Attempts to create a model of the

educational process that allows but, on the contrary, carefully hides his own leading position in the organization of the upbringing and upbringing of children.

Pedagogy of manipulation sets the teacher such a frame of interaction with the pupil, which makes him strive to create in the student a sense of independence, responsibility for what happens to him in the process of education. I must say that even by the end of the work I did not understand what type of teacher I could classify myself as: those who accept manipulation, or those who sharply reject it.

Studying this topic, I can say that manipulation is very important not only in the process of language teaching, but also in other subjects. Because in our developing age, children like to learn by being manipulated, that is, teaching science by forcing, fighting and threatening is ineffective. Therefore, I believe that it is effective to teach children science in exchange for doing something they like or doing something they like using a manipulative method.

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